

Can we protect our earth and our future ?

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Abstract

As global environmental issues become a more controversial topic, people from all over the world are now seeking a way to somehow balance the negative impacts on our earth with the human activities of economic growth. In fact, it is possible to seek such a balance. Certain harmful human activities, such as the huge consumption of fossil fuels, can be eliminated by the practice of using renewable energy, which would reduce the emission of greenhouse gases. Some might argue that renewable energy cannot fulfill our large demand for energy; however, many people are, in fact, wasting a lot of resources. From an individual perspective, we can try to save some energy by some little actions, for example, turning off air conditioning when leaving a room, which we often choose not to do. On an international level, we can try to manage the use of energy in different countries and set up collaboration schemes so that we can allocate energy in an efficient way. The development of new innovative technologies could be another benefit of such collaboration on an international level. People could possibly work together to protect this shared environment for us. The United Nations spent a lot of effort to promote such collaboration for achieving the SDGs, especially on carbon emissions. Although many progresses are achieved in the current stage through a combination of strategies and methods, including an increase in public education, international communication, and the use of carbon credits, there are still a few tricky and controversial aspects, as listed below, that we might want to take a closer look at.

1. Global Cooperation

Communication and cooperation between different countries and states in the world in acting to support the idea of sustainable development is in fact the most important. False information and the action of a single country or the unwillingness to share information in this field could cause misleading consequences including meaningless efforts. A great example would be the current situation of Japan polluting the ocean with radioactive waste. Such an event is a failure in the effort to protect the earth using the

idea of cooperation.

2. The loss of biodiversity

The current rate of species extinction is extremely high and estimated to be a thousand times higher if without influences of the human activities [1]. The impact of human activities on the environment is obvious and harmful in most cases. Although theoretical idea of focusing on the issue of biodiversity has been established for over 30 years since the United Nations have stated the objection of this in 1992 [2], the general valuation of the issue of loss in biodiversity is still a thing that we have to develop. This is also linked to the previous point of cooperation where decisions could be made at a similar level of evaluation. However, it would be a difficult decision since we have to make a choice between further developments and natural habitats.

3. The use of Natural resources

Combined with the point of protecting biodiversity, exploration of natural resources is one of the most destructive factors in human activities. The destruction of forests, mountains, and other natural capital was the result of getting trees, mines, and other useful inputs for our industrial process. In this case, both the destruction of trees and use of fossil fuels found underground would contribute to the emission of Greenhouse gases that intensify the climate problem. This climate change topic is affecting different aspects of resources and resources related to human activities [3], promoting changes such as the beginning use of new forms of energy.

4. The use of land

As part of the topic of protecting natural resources, land is an important resource to take notice of. Plantation provides humans with the necessities: food. However, as a result of land being a scarce resource and the problem of climate change, the plantation process in these limited areas has become more difficult. And in the current situation, the process of land degradation could be accelerated with many factors such as the extreme weather and the overuse of surrounding water and forests resources [3], and thus

make the efficient and protective use of land a tricky aspect in economic and ecological balance.

5. Limit of Growth?

The process where production increases with the result of a decrease in resources is in fact an economic topic. Following this economic process, environmental degradation is inevitable. As production rises, the economy tends to develop some level of consumerism that further stimulates the market and jets up the use of natural resources. The hypothesis states that demand for better environmental conditions would increase along this development, which indicates that at some point the rate of improvement of the environment would exceed the rate of destruction of environment [4]. Therefore, the point of sustainable development is not a limit of growth in economics.

6. Water management

Although more than half of the earth's surface area is covered by water, the actual amount of fresh water as a natural resource is limited. Water management is an important aspect not only because it is scarce but also because it is a important component of a natural sustainable system. Balancing competing demands from agriculture, industry, and human consumption would be challenging. Due to the issue of environmental degradation and water pollution, the quality of water might become a huge problem in most areas around the world [5] Thus, protecting water during economic growth would be a controversial aspect that we should pay attention to.

7. Government Regulation

The government is also playing a vital role in this topic of balancing economic growth and ecological conservation. However, not as tricky and controversial as the other aspects. The government should pass laws and regulatory acts that correctly target the pain point in economic activities, for example, limiting the rate of using natural resources. Recent efforts of the UN Environment Program (UNEP), World Bank, and others (UNEP et al. (1998); World Bank (1998)) demonstrate the effort in supporting changes at political level [5]. However, it is important to make precise decisions based on research and studies in order to be efficient and beneficial for protecting our environment

8. Wastes management

. Somehow similar to water resource management, it is challenging to achieve a balance state when promoting economic growth while working on waste managements. In order to minimize the effect of waste on our environment, we should promote an idea of a circular system. Promoting a circular economy, which focuses on reducing, reusing, and

recycling resources [6] would match our goal of developing a sustainable system. Wastes should not be dumped into our environment and causing pollution but should be used to generate wealth in the future.

9. Carbon Pricing

Carbon emission is one of the most common concepts mentioned in all kinds of articles. It refers to the release of greenhouse gases. Carbon dioxide in fact, could be stated as the key concept in promoting sustainable growth. Effectively achieving the process of carbon pricing would be very beneficial in working out specific plans that eliminate the emission of greenhouse gases. It is controversial because it would possibly affect some fields of industry in different ways. However, along with the challenges, it is believed that the idea of carbon Pricing can drive innovations and help stimulate the transition to a low-carbon economy [7].

10. Public Education

Last but not least, public education on the idea of sustainable development is important for us, humans, as a group in balancing economic development and ecological concerns. If without the idea of protecting earth is people's mind, human would only focus on their own benefits and "destroy" the "home" for all of us. Environmental education allows individuals to explore environmental issues and engage in problem-solving [8]. In fact, most protective actions that are beneficial in balancing the economy and ecology rely on individual efforts.

11. What can we do?

My interest in the 'UN Sustainable Development Goals: Economic Choices and Carbon Footprint-Related Analysis' project extends from witnessing huge environmental changes in rural areas of China under the Government Anti-poverty program. The economic boom was achieved at the expense of environmental degradation – deforestation, land, air and water pollution, loss of biodiversity and cultural traditions, which impacted my thoughts about business ethics. How can we thrive economically while neglecting the well-being of our environment and the people in our communities?

Joining this research project, I focused on exploring sustainable solutions for economic growth.

One effective method explored was composting, which can control carbon emissions by converting organic waste into nutrient-rich materials for agricultural practices. My experiments tested the effectiveness of composting with available materials and assessed its potential to replace chemical fertilizers. We cultivated beans in compost, regular soil, and store-bought garden soil, establishing a growth index consisting of 5 metrics: stem length, stem width, average leaf length, root length, and leaf count. The results were

promising: composting soil performed comparably to commercial gardening soil, outperforming ordinary soil. Yet, the question remains: Why isn't this method more widely adopted? A common thread emerged that the long-term sustainability solution must align with key success drivers of ease of implementation, feasibility, and return on investment.

12. Actions Taken

Building on the insights from the experiment, I established a composting pile at school and collected grass clippings, dead leaves, vegetables, and fruit scraps around our campus. I crushed these materials to create a 1-meter-high pile, transforming them into useful products for school gardening. This initiative also allowed me to test the economic feasibility of replacing traditional fertilizers. To raise community awareness, I produced and shared a video of the composting process with school faculty and students, encouraging their participation.

Simultaneously, I collaborated with Starbucks in my community, hosting seminars for their customers. I demonstrated how to recycle coffee grounds into plant fertilizer and advised on testing the effectiveness of various proportions for different plants. Additionally, I set up an online chat group for Starbucks members to share their planting progress and answer queries, with the goal of exploring a sustainable business model to enhance customer retention and brand loyalty.

Conservation practices must connect to the business world to be effective. Economic activities that degrade the environment can also fund conservation efforts, depending on how they are managed. I'm committed to continuing to raise the sustainability awareness and explore business models that could balance economic growth with ecological preservation.

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